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Distinguish between terrorism and legitimate armed resistance

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resistance**

When studying terrorist crime, it is natural to distinguish it from other forms of criminal behavior that may be mixed with it in order to determine the true magnitude of that phenomenon, which leads to distinguishing the terrorist from the ordinary criminal, which provides an opportunity to understand his personality and to identify the threat facing the State before embarking on its own policy and procedures in confronting it¹.

Since terrorism is out of the ordinary, many have confused terrorism with violent political expressions, as well as terrorism with organized crime, terrorism and legitimate armed resistance. Thus, we find that the concept of terrorism may be confused with the activities of national liberation movements and armed struggle in pursuit of independence and self-determination.

This is guaranteed by all international conventions and conventions and the Universal Declaration of Human Rights, due to the nobility of purpose and the legitimacy of the means, and the importance of this distinction is due to the prevention of colonial countries and regimes from invoking the pretext of confronting terrorism to eliminate and exterminate such legitimate movements.

Hence, we must first clarify what armed resistance is and the extent of its legitimacy, and then distinguish between terrorism and legitimate armed resistance.

The term terrorism has come to be used to describe the struggle of national liberation movements in their struggle against colonialism and racism for independence, freedom and self-determination, and has even extended to acts by other States to support and support national liberation movements and have been described as States supporting terrorism.

Some describe the act as a terrorist act, while others describe the same act as heroic.

(1) Report of the Committee on Arab, Foreign Affairs and National Security on the subject of countering terrorism, 1993, Annex No. 1 of the report (Shura Council, thirteenth ordinary session).

Some have defined legitimate armed resistance as the actions of people using armed forces in the face of a foreign occupier that raped the land and imposed its presence by force, i.e. this concept links resistance, invasion and war occupation, which was what was happening at the Brussels Conference in 1874, The Hague in 1899, and Geneva in 1949⁽¹⁾.

Another aspect of the jurisprudence was to adopt a broader definition of armed resistance, which is the combat operations carried out by national elements other than the regular armed forces in defense of national interests against foreign forces, whether these elements work within the framework of a regulation under the supervision of the actual legal authority or based on their own initiatives, whether they undertake this activity over the national territory or from outside this territory⁽²⁾.

There are close links between the right of peoples to determine their own self-determination and the principle of equal peoples' rights. Both of them constitute one of the rules of international law. This is what was stated in the report of the Subcommittee on the Elimination of Racial Discrimination on the second paragraph of Article One of the United Nations Charter "The principle of equal peoples' rights and the principle of self-determination are two components of one rule"⁽³⁾.

Accordingly, we believe that the criteria for distinguishing between terrorism and legitimate resistance are as follows:

First: The criterion of the goal: National liberation movements set before them a lofty goal, which is to achieve national independence and liberation from colonialism, so that the target of resistance operations is colonial and racist regimes or those

(1) Aziz Hasbi, *Les mouvements nationaux et le droit international*, Editions Siaucky, Rabat, 1971, pp. 22-23.

(2) Dr. Salah El-Din Amer, *Popular armed resistance in public international law*, dar al-fikr al-arabi, Cairo, 1976, pp. 40-41.

(3) United Nations Documents on International Regulation, Volume VI, page 703. /A/ 3/1/119.

who help them achieve their goals, as they are based against a foreign enemy that imposed itself by force and usurped the land with the aim of obtaining independence and leading to self-determination.

As for terrorism, it relies on illegal means and organized violence against civilian targets and unarmed victims within society, with the intention of disturbing public security to pressure political opponents or take revenge on an authority that does not meet the demands of these organizations.

Second: The legal criterion: What distinguishes the acts of violence carried out by national liberation movements is the legitimacy of these acts in the face of colonialism within the framework of what is stipulated in international resolutions and conventions that regulate the rules of military operations and the conduct of hostilities, such as the Geneva Convention of 1949, and this trend was confirmed by Resolution No. 3034 issued by the United Nations General Assembly on December 18, 1972, which affirmed the legitimacy of the armed struggle to obtain independence and reach the right to self-determination for all peoples located Under penalty of colonization.

In the same sense, the United Nations General Assembly, in its resolution No. 147/32 of December 16, 1977, condemned the acts of oppression and terrorism carried out by colonial regimes, and affirmed at its forty-fourth session the need to combat State terrorism and distinguish it from the popular struggle for self-determination in its resolution 44/29 of December 4, 1989. As for the violence and sabotage carried out by terrorist organizations, they do not enjoy any legal or international support, and there is no justification for killing innocent people, whatever the reason.

Third: The criterion of national motivation: Armed struggle operations last a long time and include targets through which the enemy suffers significant losses within a framework of popular support and sympathy, as national liberation movements rely on

the method of popular wars as a method of warfare in the face of occupation⁽¹⁾.

On the contrary, terrorist groups do not have popular or legal support, seeking to impose their demands at the expense of innocent lives.

Fourth: Organizational criterion: National liberation movements operate within an organizational framework subject to a higher authority that exercises their activities in a particular territory and takes the form of two wings, one military field that manages the fight in operations against the occupier, and the other that includes all segments of society and takes the form of an executive body that presents the issue at the internal and external levels. On the other hand, terrorist organizations differ in their organization, which follows complete secrecy and is often limited to a military wing, and there is rarely a political wing in these organizations that participates in public political life.

But here we must stop and point out that acts of armed resistance never justify the killing of innocent people in an indiscriminate manner or resort to methods of combat that are forbidden for regular armies to use in resistance, if resistance to occupation to reach the right to self-determination and independence is a legitimate demand supported by international resolutions and laws, it must practice resistance in accordance with the provisions of international law and international conventions that define their framework, controls and restrictions⁽²⁾.

(1) Dr. Al-Shafei Muhammad Bashir, Human rights law, New al-galaa library, Mansoura, 1992, p 100

(2) Dr. Ahmed Fathy Sorour, The legal confrontation of terrorism, Dar al-nahda al-arabiya, Cairo, 2008, p. 108.

This article is part of a study that we will publish later on the criteria for distinguishing between terrorist crime and the actions of armed fight against colonialism.

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